

Serruria rosea Rose spiderhead

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.6 – 1 meter in height

Distribution:

The Rose spiderhead's natural distribution is from the Du Toitskloof to the Riviersonderend Mountains, with an area of occurrence of about 51 km².

Importance:

The Rose spiderhead is one of the most delicate members of the Proteaceae family. It is classified as Near Threatened, so does not currently qualify for any of the threat categories. Due to possible future threats from afforestation, invasive alien plants and susceptibility to drought it may become threatened. *Serruria* has grown into an important member of the indigenous floriculture industry of South Africa. It is also used in the pot plant industry due to its compact size.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 34.3 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.76 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.51 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 96.7% [Single: 87.5%, Duplicated: 96.7%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 244.21 kilobases

Contig number: 7 224

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